

A Passive Bistatic Range and Doppler Sensor using a Software Defined Radio with Autocorrelation Processing of ATSC Signals

David Lang
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Individual Contributor

Abstract

A minimalist approach to moving target ranging and Doppler measurement using passive sensing is described in detail. To simplify the hardware, autocorrelation rather than cross-correlation of the reference and target signals is used. A fundamental purpose of this paper is to describe in detail a replicable passive ranging system. To that end, and to the extent practical, the use of any hardware, software, procedure or mechanical configuration that is non-transparent, proprietary or otherwise hidden is avoided.

Keywords: autocorrelation imaging, passive radar, antenna sidelobe cancellation, antenna sidelobe reduction, Doppler processing, SDR, Software Defined Radio, passive sensing.

1 Overview

Numerous papers describe the performance of passive target ranging utilizing the cross correlation of signals collected using two receivers and their associated antennas, one directed toward a target region and the other toward the target-illuminating transmitter. Currently available inexpensive software defined radio (SDR) modules can provide a continuous stream of digitized, in-phase and quadrature (IQ) baseband samples of the demodulated input signal. In practice, maintaining phase coherence between receivers has required disassembly, modification, and physical interconnection^{[2], [18]} of the SDR modules to ensure synchronization between the sampling clocks and local oscillator (LO) sources. The use of autocorrelation rather than cross-correlation results in a sensor that is physically simpler but exhibits lower target sensitivity. Ideally, the residual level of non-cancelled reference signal in the target channel should be minimized without restriction when using a cross correlation ranging system. By contrast, an autocorrelation ranging system inherently requires a reference signal level that is approximately equal to the level of the weakest anticipated target signal. If the reference signal level is increased without changing the target signal level, the target correlation output signal level increases but the apparent target to noise ratio decreases.

The ranging system described here uses:

- a single, general purpose, unmodified SDR receiver^{[24],[25]} with in-phase and quadrature sampling capability
- a single, ATSC television reference signal with high ERP
- separate reference and target receive antennas, each co-polarized with the reference transmitting antenna
- simplified transmitter reference signal reduction (cancellation)

The system was operated in a high clutter, urban environment, and the elevation above ground level for both receive antennas was restricted to ~ 4 meters. Both conditions limited the reference signal (direct signal) suppression in the target antenna path to an estimated 10 dB.

Autocorrelation is used exclusively, resulting in a worse signal to noise ratio than would be achieved with a comparable cross-correlation based system. Although incidental RF selectivity is inherent in the Yagi topology antennas, no other RF bandpass filters were used in this system. Additional baseband demodulator bandpass or lowpass filtering exists within the SDR to minimize aliasing, but detailed specifications of the filter and the related sampling rate are apparently proprietary^{[32],[33]}. A frequency stepped, constant amplitude external CW source could be used to empirically determine the internal lowpass or bandpass filter performance by comparing SDR output data file values at each frequency, but this step was not performed for the work described here.

2 Operating frequency band

Passive radar systems have generally utilized transmissions in the frequency ranges $88 \text{ MHz} \leq F_o < 800 \text{ MHz}$ ^{[1], [2], [3]} for FM and television, and $F_o \leq 3500 \text{ MHz}$ for LTE communications^[4]. Due to local receiving site restrictions, it was highly desirable to use the smallest possible antenna. An ATSC television channel with very high ERP and short wavelength was therefore selected:

KUTP AZ PHOENIX USA DT LIC
Transmit Channel: 26 542 – 548 MHz Licensed
Polarization: Horizontal (H)
Effective Radiated Power (ERP): 1000 kW ERP
Latitude Longitude
33° 20' 3.20" N
112° 3' 40.70" W To NAD27
(source: FCC database, 2017–2018)

3 Target properties

- For the system described here, the receiving site was located approximately 3 – 10 km from various Phoenix Sky Harbor airport approach paths. All data were taken during the ~20 second period that candidate aircraft were in the main beamwidth of the target antenna.
- Candidate targets for measurement were intentionally limited to aircraft with body lengths in the range 111 – 146 feet (A319 to A321). Based on a nominal body length of 128 feet, a simple stadimeter rangefinder was used to estimate the aircraft *radial* range to the site (not the terrestrial or map range).
- The aircraft velocity angle ξ (Fig. 2) is also narrowly constrained by the flight path.
- FAA guidelines^[26] set a 250 kt airspeed limit during a landing approach when the altitude is less than 10,000 feet.
- All data were recorded with both antennas horizontally polarized to match the reference transmitter polarization.
- To provide only a crude estimation of range, the target RCS σ is modeled as a fixed value of 100 square meters or $10 \cdot \log_{10}(100) = +20 \text{ dB}$. In Lim^[19] the RCS of a cylindrical target is given as

$$\text{RCS } \sigma = (2 \cdot \pi \cdot r \cdot (L^2)) / \lambda$$

so for e.g. an A320 with $L \approx 37 \text{ m}$, $r \approx 2 \text{ m}$, and $\lambda = (c / 545\text{E}+6) = 0.55$,

RCS $\sigma \approx +45 \text{ dB}$.

As simulated by an NEC model of a similar object ^[19], the RCS can vary over a 60 dB range and is critically dependent on the target's orientation relative to both the transmitter and observer.

4 Expected target and reference signal levels at receiving site

The classic bistatic target relation ^{[3], [22]} yields the target signal Pr_1 at the receiving site:

$$\begin{aligned} Pr_1 &= P_{TX} \cdot G_T \cdot G_R \cdot \lambda^2 \cdot \sigma / ((4\pi)^3 \cdot (R_1 \cdot R_2)^2) \\ &= P_{TX} + G_{TX} + G_R + 10 \cdot \log_{10}(\sigma \cdot (0.2998/Fo)^2 / ((R_1 \cdot R_2)^2 \cdot (4\pi)^3)) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

The transmitted power at the receiver site is

$$Pr_2 = P_{TX} + G_{TX} + G_{RXT} + 10 \cdot \log_{10}((0.2998/Fo)^2 / ((4\pi)^2 \cdot R_3^2)) \quad (2)$$

where:

P_{TX} = transmit (TX) radiated power, dBm

$G_T = 0$ since P_{TX} is specified as effective radiated power ERP

G_{TX} = antenna gain at the transmitter site, in the direction of the receive site

G_R = antenna gain, target to receiver (RX) site

G_{RXT} = reference antenna gain, TX to RX site, including cancellation in dB¹

R_1 = range, TX to target, as listed

$R_2 = R_1 - R_3$ = range, target to site, as listed

R_3 = range, TX to RX site

Fo = transmit frequency in GHz

$(0.2998/Fo)$ = wavelength in meters

σ = target radar cross section (RCS) in m², as listed

Pr_1 = target signal at RX input, dBm

Pr_2 = TX signal at RX input, dBm

1 Two antennas are used in the RF processing portion of the system, as shown in Fig. 1. The reference signal antenna alone exhibits gain G_{RMX} when oriented toward the reference transmitter, and gain G_{RMN} in the direction of the target. The target signal antenna has gain G_R in the target direction and gain G_{MMT} in the direction of the reference transmitter. In the system described here, the physical orientation of both antennas is first adjusted and then frozen in order to approximately minimize G_{MMT} and maximize G_{RMX} . The relationship of G_{RMX} to G_{RXT} is summarized in the next section.

Fig. 1 gain conventions in free space

For a receiving site configuration like Fig. 2, the reference signal level will inherently be much greater than the target signal level at the receiving site and would fundamentally limit the system's target sensitivity. For this work, the target and reference antennas were substantially identical, and had a simulated forward lobe beamwidth of $\pm 20 = 40$ degrees at the (peak gain -3dB) points. The antenna pattern detail and broadband impedance data for both the modeled and fabricated antennas are summarized in the Appendix.

In most of the passive radar papers reviewed, the reduction of direct-path, reference signal level in the target channel is accomplished in the data processing step and not within the antenna arrays or RF interconnect paths^{[2],[18]}. Historically, the term 'antenna sidelobe cancellation' was often conflated with the related concept 'antenna array steering'. A task common to both concepts was the determination of an optimal adjustment of passive networks that linearly sums the output of individual antennas within an array so that the entire antenna array simultaneously exhibits maximum gain at a desired target bearing angle and minimum gain or nulls at N different 'jammer' bearing angles. For this paper, the task is the much simpler special case wherein the bearing angles of both a single target and a single reference signal source are fixed or moving slowly.

Assume that V_1 and V_2 are target and reference signal voltage levels as measured at the receive site with an isotropic antenna, and that antenna gains initially defined in dB are replaced with the equivalent voltage gains, e.g. $G_R = 10^{(G_R / 20)}$. A three port network including an adjustable, complex multiplier or weight (block W2 in Figs. 23 and A.3.1) is inserted between both antenna ports and the SDR receiver input port.

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_3 &= \text{target antenna output voltage} = V_1 \cdot G_R + V_2 \cdot G_{MMT} \\
 V_4 &= \text{reference antenna output voltage} = V_2 \cdot G_{RMX} + V_1 \cdot G_{RMN} \\
 V_5 &= \text{SDR input voltage} = E_S \text{ from Fig. 23}
 \end{aligned}$$

For the next analysis the symbol U_2 denotes the complex multiplier U_2 / θ_2 . Similarly, the four antenna transfer functions $G_R \dots G_{RMN}$ and the V_1, V_2 voltages are complex.

Assume that the transmitter emits only an unmodulated CW signal, and a Doppler frequency shift is applied by the target.

$$V_5 = \text{SDR input RF voltage} = V_3 + (U_2 \cdot V_4) \\ = V_1 \cdot G_R\$ + V_2 \cdot G_{\text{MMT}}\$ + U_2 \cdot V_2 \cdot G_{\text{RMX}}\$ + U_2 \cdot V_1 \cdot G_{\text{RMN}}\$$$

For the CW signal, the amplitude and phase of U_2 can adjusted so that:

$$V_2 \cdot G_{\text{MMT}}\$ = -(U_2 \cdot V_2 \cdot G_{\text{RMX}}\$) \\ U_2 = \pm G_{\text{MMT}}\$ / G_{\text{RMX}}\$$$

and the 'direct' contribution from the transmitter (via G_{MMT} and G_{RMX} only) is reduced to zero. For this special case, let $V_6 = V_{5(\text{DIRECT})}$:

$$V_6 = V_1 \cdot G_R\$ + U_2 \cdot V_1 \cdot G_{\text{RMN}}\$$$

Now let

$$G_{\text{MMT}}\$ = G_R\$ / \text{FB}_{\text{target}} \\ G_{\text{RMN}}\$ = G_{\text{RMX}}\$ / \text{FB}_{\text{reference}}$$

where $\text{FB}_{\text{target}}$ and $\text{FB}_{\text{reference}}$ are the forward / reverse (or front / back) antenna pattern complex *voltage* ratios, and each are > 1 .

$$V_6 = V_1 \cdot (G_R\$ + (G_{\text{MMT}}\$ / G_{\text{RMX}}\$) \cdot G_{\text{RMN}}\$) \\ = V_1 \cdot (G_R\$ + (G_R\$ / (\text{FB}_{\text{target}} \cdot \text{FB}_{\text{reference}})))$$

$$\max(V_6) = V_1 \cdot G_R\$ \cdot (1 + \text{Re}(1 / (\text{FB}_{\text{target}} \cdot \text{FB}_{\text{reference}}))) \\ \min(V_6) = V_1 \cdot G_R\$ \cdot (1 - \text{Re}(1 / (\text{FB}_{\text{target}} \cdot \text{FB}_{\text{reference}})))$$

Assume that both antennas exhibit mediocre directivity, e.g. front/back ≈ 12 dB corresponding to a front/back *voltage* ratio $\text{FB}_{\text{target}} = \text{FB}_{\text{reference}} \approx 4$

Then

$$20 \cdot \log_{10}(\max(V_6)/ \min(V_6)) \approx 1 \text{ dB}$$

Thus the solution which reduces the CW reference signal component to zero can change the target signal level by ± 0.5 dB . Due to the wide bandwidth of an ATSC signal, and the time delay between the direct signal (via $G_{\text{RMX}}\$$) and close range clutter (via $G_R\$$) can only be approximately cancelled using a single weight block like W2.

For this autocorrelation system, and as detailed later in § 11, the output target to noise ratio is maximized when both the reference signal and the target signal levels are equal at the SDR port. For almost all realistic values of target cross section and range values R_3 and R_2 , the reference signal level greatly exceeds the target signal level (Table 1).

Fig. 2 range and azimuth definitions

At the test site (north Phoenix, AZ) the predicted (co-polarized) bistatic levels for some limiting cases of range and target σ are:

- $P_{TX} = +90$ dBm
- $G_{TX} = 0$ dB
- $F_0 = 0.545$ GHz
- $G_R = 11.7$ dB
- $R_3 = 19$ km
- $R_2 = R_1 - R_3$

σ m ²	G_{RXT}	G_R	R_1	R_2	Pr_1	Pr_2
20	-10	11.7	22400	3400	-81.09	-32.75
40	-20	17.0	41000	22000	-94.25	-42.75

It was empirically evident that reference signal cancellation using *only* a single-stage RF canceller (Fig. A.3.1) appeared to be limited to ~ 10 dB due to uncontrollable reflection from nearby structures and vegetation at the available test site. Without further qualification, Lim^[19] suggests that up to 15 dB of reference signal cancellation is obtainable by simply rotating the target receive antenna from a co-polarized to a cross-polarized orientation. This option was not exploited in any of the measurements summarized below.

Extensive RCS modeling of an aircraft^[19] using NEC code illustrates the difficulty of quantifying the relative advantages of cross-polarization versus co-polarization of the target receive antenna. A plot of the simulated RCS of a single aircraft model, using co-polarized transmit and receive antennas (Fig. 34^[19]) shows two RCS maxima (+ 29 dBi and +35 dBi peak) at target orientations $\theta = \pm 90$ degrees (i.e. side aspect view of the aircraft body) as would be expected. The angular width of the RCS for either maxima was $\sim \pm 3$ degrees at the -3 dBi points. For almost all other azimuth angles the RCS decreased to $\sim +10$ dBi.

5 Software defined radio (SDR) module detail

The output from the SDR^{[24], [27], [33], [37]} consists of serially formatted (USB) 8 bit signed bytes comprising interleaved, in-phase (I) and quadrature (Q) digitized values of the SDR baseband demodulator outputs. For the system described here, the default SDR sample rate S_R was set to 1.024 MSPS. Note that the I and Q demodulator outputs are sampled at the same instant, and it is common practice to refer to the data *pair* as ‘a sample’.

In order to determine the phase convention of the demodulated outputs, the SDR was set to 545.000 MHz, an external signal source was set to $F = 545.00074$ MHz, and a data file was recorded for $4.0E+5$ samples at $S_R = 1.024E+6$. For this test case, the plotted IMX(*) data lags the REX(*) data by 90 degrees (see Appendix). The effective SDR *bandwidth* prior to sampling was not physically verified.

The host software used here (gqrx^[23]) commands the SDR to save a specified number of contiguous samples at a specified sample rate to a data file in byte format. In this sense the system is not ‘real time’ or ‘continuous’ since the data is saved in finite batches, and the processed result of a batch containing a valid target appears as a single point on a plot of range and Doppler frequency.

6 Data batch length and Doppler frequency limits

V_T is the *apparent* target velocity relative to the path between the target, the receiving site and the transmitting source. Due to the unique location of the receiving site, all target data was collected when the target was positioned approximately along the path from the transmitter to the site, as shown in Fig. 2. In this case, V_T is dependent only on the radial speed and velocity angle ξ .

For a signal traversing the receiver-to-target-receiver path, the range resolution is $\Delta x_1 \approx (c / (2 \cdot S_R))$.

As detailed in the next section, a single batch of contiguous SDR data samples of length N_{\max} is required for a range-Doppler analysis. A target moving at speed V_T moves a distance

$$\Delta x_2 = N_{\max} \cdot V_T / S_R .$$

and also shifts the transmitted reference signal by the Doppler offset frequency

$$\Delta F_0 = (2 \cdot V_T / c) \cdot F_0 .$$

When $\Delta x_2 \gg \Delta x_1$, target responses will appear in adjacent range locations. In the case where $\Delta x_2 = \Delta x_1$

$$c / (2 \cdot S_R) = N_{\max} \cdot V_T / S_R$$

$$N_{\max} = c / (2 \cdot V_T)$$

thus for $V_T = 250$ kt = 128.6 m/s, $N_{\max} = 1.166E+6$

and for $F_0 = 0.545$ GHz, $S_R = 1.024$ MSPS, $N_{\max} = 512 \cdot 512 = 262144$,

Doppler frequency = 467.5 Hz, batch duration = $262144 \cdot S_R = 0.256$ sec.

7 Data processing architecture

Visual Basic^[28] was used exclusively to create executable code for all FFT and IFFT data processing and the graphical display of range and Doppler plots. The processing utilizes standard, open source FFT and IFFT code^{[14],[29]} and should be easily replicable with other languages.

When reading an SDR data file, the VB software initially converts the data from byte format to signed integer format and assigns the data to one long matrix $SH(n)$. The data is then processed using *at least* two independent paths:

- a range FFT of length m followed by a Doppler FFT of length p (case 1)
- a range FFT of length s followed by a Doppler FFT of length q (case 2)

Although the algorithm is detailed for cases 1 and 2, the finalized ranging code uses four cases. For all four cases, the product of the range FFT size and Doppler FFT size will be a constant N_{\max} .

Each case is processed using the same overall sequence shown in Fig. 3. The $SH(n)$ values are de-interleaved and assigned to consecutive I samples $REX(n)$ and consecutive Q samples $IMX(n)$ according to:

```
 $j = 0$  to  $(p - 1)$  step 1  
   $k = 0$  to  $(m - 1)$  step 1  
     $REX(n) = SH(((2 \cdot k) + 1) + 2 \cdot j \cdot m)$   
     $IMX(n) = SH(((2 \cdot k) + 2) + 2 \cdot j \cdot m)$   
  next  $k$   
next  $j$ 
```

where j and k are temporary variables.

Fig. 3 Data path for the default range–Doppler processing code

Both the main FFT and inverse FFT (IFFT) subroutines were adapted directly from Press^[29] and rewritten to be compatible with VB. For both algorithms, the I and Q components of the input data are matrices $REX(*)$ and $IMX(*)$. When exiting each subroutine, the contents of the matrices $REX(*)$ and $IMX(*)$ are replaced with the computed results. This data handling convention was retained in the VB versions utilized herein. The inputs to the IFFT are then $REX(n) = (RBX(n))^2$ and $IMX(n) = 0$.

The output of the IFFT is assigned to matrices $UAV(r,n) = REX(n)$ and $UCV(r,n) = -IMX(n)$, comprising n range values for the r -th group of adjacent samples.

Under *pseudostationary target* conditions, the operating wavelength is small enough to generate a significant Doppler frequency offset during the time that the target remains inside a single range sample n . If the moving target is located in range cell $n = \mathcal{P}$, the sequences of IFFT output values

$$UAV(1, \mathcal{P}), UAV(2, \mathcal{P}) \dots UAV(\max(r), \mathcal{P}) \text{ and} \\ UCV(1, \mathcal{P}), UCV(2, \mathcal{P}) \dots UCV(\max(r), \mathcal{P})$$

will exhibit sinusoidal amplitude envelopes, as shown in Figs. 9 and 10. This pair of sequences is analyzed by the final FFT at each n to yield a range–Doppler plot.

The squared magnitude of the final Doppler FFT output is

$$REK(r,n) = REX(r,n)^2 + IMX(r,n)^2$$

These are optionally averaged across adjacent Doppler bin values and assigned to new matrices RYA(*,*) RYF(*,*). The distinction between these four matrices can be clarified by initially focusing on the first two matrices RYA(*,*) and RYB(*,*).

With the exception of specific matrix row and column sizes, subsequent operations on RYE(*,*) and RYF(*,*) will be identical to those on RYA(*,*) and RYB(*,*).

For the first two cases,

$$RYA(p,m) = REK(r,n) , \quad \max(r) = \mathcal{R}_1 \text{ and } \max(n) = N_1$$

$$RYB(q,s) = REK(r,n) , \quad \max(r) = \mathcal{R}_2 \text{ and } \max(n) = N_2$$

where $(\mathcal{R}_1 \cdot N_1 = \mathcal{R}_2 \cdot N_2)$ is the total sample size N_{\max} and must be the same for each RYA(*,*), RYB(*,*)... RYF(*,*).

8 Coincidence algorithm (sieve filter) detail

Assume that an input data batch consists of ergodic random noise plus a *single* moving target. Elements of the output matrices RYA(p , m) and RYB(q , s) that exceed a specified amplitude threshold are assigned to new matrices A(e , f) and B(g , h) respectively. All other matrix locations in A(*,*) and B(*,*) are set to zero. The total number of nonzero locations is $|A \cup B| - w$ where the (w) term includes the w target locations in both A(*,*) and B(*,*). Although it is beyond the scope of this paper to quantify the phenomenon, simulation results show that when both the system gain and detection threshold are adjusted such that approximately half of the matrix elements in A(*,*) and B(*,*) are nonzero, the number of nonzero elements *common* to both A and B is $(|A \cap B| - w) < [0.5 \cdot (|A \cup B| - w)]$.

Stated another way, outputs exceeding the detection threshold from both process paths fall into two categories:

$A(e_1 , f_1) > 0$ and $B(g_1 , h_1) > 0$, $e_1 = g_1$ and $f_1 = h_1$
 – output values indistinguishable from 'actual' targets

$A(e_3 , f_3) > 0$ and $B(g_3 , h_3) > 0$, $e_3 \neq g_3$ or $f_3 \neq h_3$
 – spurious correlation outputs

Graphically, $|A \cap B|$ is the overlap region (Fig. 4) between A(*,*) and B(*,*).

Fig. 4 The intersection of the two data sets

case 1: $p = 0$ to \mathcal{R}_1 ; $m = 0$ to N_1

case 2: $q = 0$ to \mathcal{R}_2 ; $m = 0$ to N_2

Let

$U =$ the smaller of \mathcal{R}_1 or \mathcal{R}_2

$V =$ the smaller of N_1 or N_2

For $j = 0$ to U

For $k = 0$ to V

$$UYD(j, k) = RYA(j, k) \cdot RYB(j, k) \quad (3)$$

Next k

Next j

Since $(\mathcal{R}_1 \cdot N_1 = \mathcal{R}_2 \cdot N_2)$ must by definition be constant, the total number of Doppler cycles processed in both cases is the same, and the final resolved FFT frequency (as FFT Doppler output matrix indices) will be the same for both cases 1 and 2 in the overlap region bounded by $(0,0$ to $\mathcal{R}_2, N_1)$.

For all four cases $RYA(*,*) \dots RYF(*,*)$, the assignment (3) is replaced by

For $j = 0$ to U'

For $k = 0$ to V'

$$UYD(j, k) = RYA(j, k) \cdot RYB(j, k) \cdot RYE(j, k) \cdot RYF(j, k) \quad (4)$$

Next k

Next j

where

$U' =$ the smallest column dimension of $RYA(*,*) \dots RYF(*,*)$

$V' =$ the smallest row dimension of $RYA(*,*) \dots RYF(*,*)$

The decision to use the sieve filter ultimately depends on which of the following is deemed more desirable:

- (a) set the detection threshold to zero, allowing the detection of all possible weak targets *and* large spurious signals (misclassified targets) , or
- (b) reject large spurious signals, *and* preclude the detection of some weak signals, by utilizing a non-zero threshold.

The default code, which incorporates the steps in Fig. 3, the sieve filter, and all display processing is the VB project IFFT_U_10K_4M7.xxx, hereafter abbreviated *4M7.xxx.

A synthetic target test file (§ 9, below) was generated with a target time delay of 49 samples, and a Doppler count of 33 cycles per batch size of $512 \cdot 512 = 262144$ samples.

For this case,

$$\begin{aligned}
 N_1 &= 256, & R_1 &= 1024 \\
 N_2 &= 512, & R_2 &= 512 \\
 N_3 &= 128, & R_3 &= 2048 \\
 N_4 &= 1024, & R_4 &= 256
 \end{aligned}$$

Fig. 5 The range–Doppler output using the plotted values

$$\text{Sqr}(\text{RYA}(*,*) \cdot \text{RYB}(*,*) \cdot \text{RYE}(*,*) \cdot \text{RYF}(*,*))$$

The cursor location within the plot area yields the Doppler frequency (both as cycles per batch size and cycles per second) and the range (both as delay offset N and the delay in meters), all highlighted in blue text. At the sample interval $9.766E-7$ sec per range cell, the synthetic target signal is delayed by $49.0 \cdot 9.766E-7 = 4.785E-5$ sec corresponding to $4.82E-5 \cdot 2.998E+8 \text{ m/s} = 1.435E+4 \text{ m}$.

The specified batch size ($N_1 \cdot R_1$) and sample interval determine the batch process interval. The Doppler frequency for a selected point is then

$$\text{Doppler (Hz)} = \text{Doppler(cycles)} / ((N_1 \cdot R_1) \cdot T_{\text{sample}})$$

For the same test file, the code *4M7.xxx was temporarily modified to show RYA(*,*) only, RYB(*,*) only, or the sieve filter output (RYA(*,*) • RYB(*,*)):

Fig. 6 The range Doppler output for RYA(*,*)^2 only

Fig. 7 The range Doppler output for RYB(*,*)^2 only

Fig. 8 The range Doppler output for the sieve filter output $RYA(*,*) \cdot RYB(*,*)^2$

Note that in the above plots (1), (2) the values actually plotted are $RYA(*,*)^2$ and $RYB(*,*)^2$ in order to ensure dimensional consistency with the composite value $RYA(*,*) \cdot RYB(*,*)$.

All gain values VGAN were adjusted to yield the same value UUMAX for the actual target. Items originally visible in either $RYA(*,*)^2$ or $RYB(*,*)^2$ plot are barely visible in the grey outlined areas.

9 Synthetic target data files

In order to *verify* the target detection process (Fig. 3), it was first necessary to create an empirically derived model of the ATSC signal amplitude distribution. A synthetic target file comprises two long matrices. The first matrix MKA(n) is generated by successive calls to the derived ATSC random amplitude noise subroutine NOISEB(), as detailed below. A second matrix AKA(n) is a sequence of uniformly distributed random phases. Note that within VB, each evaluation of the expression Rnd(1) yields a different pseudorandom floating point number².

$$\begin{aligned} \text{MKA}(n) &= \text{V9} \quad (\text{output variables, subroutines NOISEA(), NOISEB(), below}) \\ \text{AKA}(n) &= 2 \cdot \pi \cdot \text{Rnd}(1) \end{aligned}$$

These are transformed to real and complex sequences as:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{SHI}(n) &= \text{MKA}(n) \cdot \cos(\text{AKA}(n)) \\ \text{SHQ}(n) &= \text{MKA}(n) \cdot \cos(\text{AKA}(n) + \pi/2) \end{aligned}$$

and the target signal is a delayed (and Doppler rotated) version of the reference signal:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{SJI}(n - Z) &= \text{MKA}(n) \cdot \cos(\text{AKA}(n) - (2 \cdot \pi \cdot \text{KAA} \cdot n / \text{nmax})) & (5) \\ \text{SJQ}(n - Z) &= \text{MKA}(n) \cdot \cos(\text{AKA}(n) - (2 \cdot \pi \cdot \text{KAA} \cdot n / \text{nmax}) + \pi/2) & (6) \end{aligned}$$

where the independent variables are:

KAA = an integral number of target Doppler cycles
nmax = the number of samples over which KAA occurs, e.g. 262144 = 512 • 512
Z = the (target – reference) signal differential time delay, as an integer number of SDR sample intervals:

$$Z = (2 \cdot R_2) \cdot S_R / c \quad (7)$$

The reference and target signals are scaled by K₄ and K₂ and the signals are summed, as:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{FKI}(n - Z) &= \text{Int}(127 \cdot (\text{K}_2 \cdot \text{SJI}(n) + \text{K}_4 \cdot \text{SHI}(n))) \\ \text{If } \text{FKI}(n - Z) > 128 &\text{ Then } \text{FKI}(n - Z) = 128 & (8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{If } \text{FKI}(n - Z) < (-127) \text{ Then } \text{FKI}(n - Z) = -127 \quad (9)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{FKQ}(n - Z) &= \text{Int}(127 \cdot (\text{K}_2 \cdot \text{SJQ}(n) + \text{K}_4 \cdot \text{SHQ}(n))) \\ \text{If } \text{FKQ}(n - Z) > 128 &\text{ Then } \text{FKQ}(n - Z) = 128 & (10) \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{If } \text{FKQ}(n - Z) < (-127) \text{ Then } \text{FKQ}(n - Z) = -127 \quad (11)$$

The final synthetic target data is saved as the interleaved sequence FKI(n - Z), FKQ(n - Z) as a text file.

When analyzing a synthetic target file e.g. TEST_BBBE_HCK6S_15D.txt, the IFFT real and imaginary output matrices $UAV(r,n) = REX(r,n)$ and $UCV(r,n) = -IMX(r,n)$ were plotted to verify the phasing convention. The time origin $t = 0$ is always located at the bottom left corner of all plots.

For creating *_HCK6S_15D.txt, $K_2 = 0.30$, the range was set to 48, and the Doppler count set to 32 cycles over the entire generated file length $512 \cdot 512 = 262144$.

To clarify the phase relationship the plot window is limited to only a small fraction of the available $512 \cdot 512$ range of $UAV(*,*)$ or $UCV(*,*)$, i.e. $(80/512)$ of the maximum Doppler value and $(90/512)$ of the maximum range value. The plotted range value is clearly correct at $48/90 \approx 53\%$ of full scale, and similarly the Doppler value is $(32 \cdot 80 / 512) = 5.0$ cycles.

Fig. 9 The imaginary part of the range IFFT output ($-IMX(r,n)$) vs. time

Fig. 10 The real part of the range IFFT output ($REX(r,n)$) vs. time

Doppler resolution is also degraded by target Doppler phase scintillation. The net reflected signal from an extended, rotating target may exhibit large phase fluctuations due to individual reflections from proximal or distal regions on the target that are alternately or periodically dominant, e.g. when an additional phase envelope of M cycles per (batch size n_{max}) is imposed upon the target signal.

$$\varphi = (\pi / 2) \cdot \text{Sgn}(\sin(M \cdot (2\pi \cdot n / n_{max})))$$

$$\text{SJI}(n - Z) = \text{MKA}(n) \cdot \cos(\varphi + \text{AKA}(n) - (2 \cdot \pi \cdot \text{KAA} \cdot n / n_{max}))$$

$$\text{SJQ}(n - Z) = \text{MKA}(n) \cdot \cos(\varphi + \text{AKA}(n) - (2 \cdot \pi \cdot \text{KAA} \cdot n / n_{max}) + \pi/2)$$

To verify this effect, a synthetic target file was generated using $M = 5$ and $\text{KAA} = 33$. The range-Doppler result (Fig. 11) is resolved into two Doppler bins at $33 \pm 5 = 38$ and 28 cycles per batch, and the 33 cycle result is suppressed.

Fig. 11 The Doppler FFT output with severe Doppler phase stepping.

10 Noise model detail

The next slides are histograms of the amplitude distributions of an actual ATSC signal received by the SDR and of the generated synthetic signal data after optimizing the ATSC noise model. Both cases represent the reference source only, with no target present. For the actual ATSC signal this condition applies when only the reference antenna is used. For generation of the synthetic signal, the K_2 (target amplitude) constant was set to zero. In both data sets, the absolute value of an $FKI(n)$ data point is allocated to the corresponding histogram slot.

The histogram exhibits a peak at the $\text{abs}(FKI(n)) \geq 127$ slot because both the SDR physical gain and the synthetic data code were adjusted so that the percentage of samples with amplitudes $\{+128, -127\}$ was less than or equal to 1%.

The close match between the SDR and synthetic data was achieved solely by empirically adjusting the parameters within the $NOISEB()$ model. By contrast, it was not possible to achieve a histogram match between the SDR data and a normal (Gaussian) distribution noise model³ by adjusting any of the Gaussian model parameters, as illustrated in Figs. 13 and 14.

Although not shown here, the histogram profile of the ATSC $FKQ(n)$ data is essentially identical to that shown for the $FKI(n)$ data, as would be expected. A partial code listing for the synthetic data algorithm is included in the Appendix.

2 For a large number of evaluations, the distribution of $Rnd(1)$ is uniform over the range $0 < Rnd(1) < 1$. Detailed accounts of nonrandom periodicities encountered when using $Rnd(1)$ can be found in ^{[30], [31]}

3 The normal distribution generator $NOISEA()$ used here is the conventional Box–Muller representation with an additional limit applied to prevent underflow of variable $S1$, as shown.

Fig. 12 Comparison of actual ATSC data file vs. ATSC model

The noise model used for the synthetic target file
 TEST_BBBE_HGM7S_17H2xA.txt
 was:

```

Private Sub NOISEB()
  S1 = Rnd(1)
  S2 = Rnd(1)
  If S1 < 0.0001 Then S1 = 0.0001
  S3 = -2 * (0.25 * Log(S1))
  If S3 < 0 Then S3 = 0
  V9 = 0.785 * Sqr(S3)
End Sub

```

For the sole purpose of verifying the accuracy of the noise model NOISEB(), code lines (8) to (11) were included as previously listed in § 9, thereby limiting FK_I(n) and FK_Q(n) to the range {-127, 128}. For both the model and the SDR data the saturation rate was ≤ 1.0%

Fig. 13 Comparison of actual ATSC data file vs. Gaussian model #1

The noise model used for the synthetic target file TEST_BBBE_HGM7S_18ss.txt was:

```
Private Sub NOISEA()
  S1 = Rnd(1)
  S2 = Rnd(1)
  If S1 < 0.0001 Then S1 = 0.0001
  S3 = -2 * Log(S1)
  If S3 < 0 Then S3 = 0
  V9 = 1.0 * Sqr(S3) * Cos(2 * pi * S2)
End Sub
```

It was not possible to achieve a match between the SDR (ATSC) data and synthetic data produced by Gaussian noise generator NOISEA() under any conditions, including enabling or disabling the amplitude limiting code lines (8) to (11). In the above plot, the model values FKI(n) were *not* limited to $\{-127, 128\}$.

Fig. 14 Comparison of actual ATSC data file vs. Gaussian model #2

Private Sub NOISEA()

S1 = Rnd(1)

S2 = Rnd(1)

If S1 < 0.0001 Then S1 = 0.0001

S3 = -2 * Log(S1)

If S3 < 0 Then S3 = 0

V9 = 0.5 * Sqr(S3) * Cos(2 * π * S2)

End Sub

It was not possible to achieve a match between the SDR (ATSC) data and synthetic data produced by Gaussian noise generator NOISEA() under any conditions, including enabling or disabling the amplitude limiting code lines (8) to (11). In the above plot, the model values FKI(n) were *not* limited to $\{-127, 128\}$.

11 Autocorrelation Range–Doppler process gain

Based on the results in both § 9 and § 10 , the synthetic target code exhibits the correct NOISEB() model statistics and also correct target values in the range–Doppler analysis code *4M7.xxx. Within either the target generation code or *4M7.xxx , there is no inherent restriction⁴ on the numeric magnitude of any variable, other than in Eqns. (8) to (11). Accordingly, we could hypothetically replace the (actual) 8 bit resolution SDR with another SDR which incorporates a much higher resolution A/D but is otherwise identical to the original SDR. In this case, the outputs of the two SDRs would be indistinguishable under the conditions in Fig. 12, and the limits (8) to (11) can be deleted, permitting target generation for arbitrarily large values of K_4 and K_2 .

The following analytic expressions were empirically derived after comparison to the simulation results for both the ATSC and Gaussian noise models. For the Gaussian model NOISEA() the output line is arbitrarily scaled as $V9 = \mathbf{1.0} \cdot \text{Sqr}(U3) \cdot \text{Cos}(2 \cdot \pi \cdot S2)$ as shown in Fig. 13 .

$$\text{SLP} = ((\text{NTT}_1 - Z) / \text{NTT}_1) \quad \text{where } 0 < Z < \text{NTT}_1 \quad (12)$$

where Z is the sample delay (Eqn. 5)

$$\text{GYK} = \text{Sqr}((\text{SLP} \cdot K_4 \cdot K_2 \cdot \text{NTT}_1)^2 + \text{DCW}^2) \quad (13)$$

$$\text{DCW} = \text{Sqr}(\text{NTT}_1) \cdot (K_4^2 + K_2^2 + [(K_2^2) \cdot (K_4^2) / (K_2^2 + K_4^2)]) \quad (14)$$

where GYK is the RMS value of the target IFFT output amplitude in range bin Z , and DCW is the RMS value of non–target IFFT output amplitudes averaged across all range bins $\neq Z$. Note that the 'slip' factor SLP by itself has no effect on the contents of bins not in the target range.

The FFT output components in the target Doppler cell are:

$$\text{FCM} = \text{Sqr}((\text{SLP} \cdot K_4 \cdot K_2 \cdot \text{NTT}_1 \cdot \text{NTT}_2)^2 + \text{FDW}^2) \quad (15)$$

$$\text{FDW} = \text{Sqr}(\text{NTT}_2 \cdot \text{NTT}_1) \cdot (K_4^2 + K_2^2 + [(K_2^2) \cdot (K_4^2) / (K_2^2 + K_4^2)]) \quad (16)$$

where FCM is the RMS value of the target FFT output amplitude in range bin Z , and FDW is the RMS value of non–target FFT output amplitudes averaged across all range bins $\neq Z$.

4 The range of single–precision variables in VB^[28] is cited as approximately 3.4E+38 to 1.4E–45 and –3.4E+38 to –1.4E–45

The GYK, SLP, FCM and FDW shown above represent the RMS values of a large number P of trials wherein the NTT_1 , NTT_2 , K_2 , K_4 , and SLP values are frozen during the P trials and only the random sequences (scaled by K_2 and K_4) are changed during a particular trial.

Note that in all of the following, the term 'analytic values' (15) and (16) are applied to *both* the Gaussian and ATSC noise model cases.

Fig. 15 Doppler FFT output amplitude ratio FCM/FDW, ATSC simulation vs analytic model as a function of K_2 with constant K_4 and $SLP = 0.90625 = (1 - 48/512)$.

Fig. 16 Doppler FFT output amplitude ratio FCM/FDW, Gaussian simulation vs analytic values as a function of K_2 with constant K_4 and $SLP = 0.90625 = (1 - 48/512)$.

Fig. 17 Doppler FFT *target* output amplitude FCM, ATSC simulation vs. analytic values as a function of K_2 with constant K_4 and $SLP = 0.90625 = (1 - 48/512)$

Fig. 18 Doppler FFT *target* output amplitude FCM, Gaussian simulation vs. analytic values as a function of K_2 with constant K_4 and $SLP = 0.90625 = (1 - 48/512)$

$$(FCM_{(analytic)} / FCM_{ATSC(simulated)}) \approx 3.26..$$

$$(FCM_{(analytic)} / FCM_{Gaussian(simulated)}) \approx 1.0$$

Fig. 19 Doppler FFT *non-target* output amplitude FDW, ATSC simulation vs. analytic values as a function of K_2 with constant K_4 and $SLP = 0.90625 = (1 - 48/512)$

Fig. 20 Doppler target FFT *non-target* output amplitude FDW, Gaussian simulation vs. analytic values as a function of K_2 with constant K_4 and $SLP = 0.90625 = (1 - 48/512)$

$$(FDW_{(analytic)} / FDW_{ATSC(simulated)}) \approx 3.26..$$

$$(FDW_{(analytic)} / FDW_{Gaussian(simulated)}) \approx 1.0$$

Comparing figs. 17 and 19,

$$(FCM_{(analytic)} / FCM_{ATSC(simulated)}) \approx (FDW_{(analytic)} / FDW_{ATSC(simulated)}) \approx 3.26..$$

So that

$$\left(\frac{FCM_{\text{Gaussian}}}{FDW_{\text{Gaussian}}} \right) \approx \left(\frac{FCM_{\text{ATSC}}}{FDW_{\text{ATSC}}} \right)$$

Stated another way, the analytic values (15) and (16) yield accurate (FCM / FDW) ratios for both the Gaussian and ATSC simulation values.

Fig. 21 Doppler FFT output amplitude ratio FCM/FDW, Gaussian simulation (s) vs analytic model (a) as a function of K_2 with two values of K_4 and $SLP = 0.90625 = (1 - 48/512)$

To simplify (15) and (16) in the *weak signal* case, let

$$\begin{aligned} \text{FCM}/\text{FDW} &= \text{Sqr}((\text{SLP} \cdot \text{K}_4 \cdot \text{K}_2 \cdot \text{NTT}_1 \cdot \text{NTT}_2)^2 + \text{FDW}^2) / \text{FDW} = \\ &\text{Sqr}(((\text{SLP} \cdot \text{K}_4 \cdot \text{K}_2 \cdot \text{NTT}_1 \cdot \text{NTT}_2)^2 + \text{FDW}^2) / \text{FDW}^2) = \\ &\text{Sqr}(((\text{SLP} \cdot \text{K}_4 \cdot \text{K}_2 \cdot \text{NTT}_1 \cdot \text{NTT}_2)^2 / \text{FDW}^2) + 1) \end{aligned}$$

In the weak signal case, $\text{K}_2 \ll \text{K}_4$ and $\text{FDW} \approx (\text{K}_4^2) \cdot \text{Sqr}(\text{NTT}_1 \cdot \text{NTT}_2)$

Then

$$\text{FCM}/\text{FDW} \approx \text{Sqr}(((\text{SLP}^2 \cdot \text{K}_2^2 \cdot \text{NTT}_1 \cdot \text{NTT}_2) / (\text{K}_4^2)) + 1) \quad (17)$$

e.g for $\text{NTT}_1 = \text{NTT}_2 = 512$, $\text{SLP} = 0.906$, $\text{K}_4 = 127$, and $\text{K}_2 = 1.27$,
 $\text{FCM}/\text{FDW} \approx 4.746536$

processing gain $\approx 20 \cdot \log_{10} (4.74 / (1.27 / 127)) = 53.5 \text{ dB}$

Table 1 summarizes the predicted target range performance for six different scenarios using the independent variables

$$\text{NTT}_1, \text{NTT}_2, \text{S}_R, \text{SLP}, \text{F}_0, \text{R}_3, \text{RCS}, \text{G}_R, \text{G}_{\text{RXT}}, \text{G}_{\text{TX}}, \text{P}_{\text{TX}} \text{ and } (\text{R}_1 \text{ or } \text{R}_2) \quad (18)$$

and the dependent variables are

$$\text{Pr}_1, \text{Pr}_2, (\text{FCM}/\text{FDW}) \quad (19)$$

The received target and reference power levels Pr_1 (Eqn. 1) and Pr_2 (Eqn. 2) must be converted to voltages at the input to the range–Doppler process (Eqns. 13,14):

$$\text{K}_2 = 10^{(\text{Pr}_1 / 20)}$$

$$\text{K}_4 = 10^{(\text{Pr}_2 / 20)}$$

Table 1 Theoretical Range Performance

SYSTEM SUMMARY	case(1)	case(2)	case(3)	case(4)
NTT1	512.00	512.00	512.00	1024.00
NTT2	512.00	512.00	512.00	512.00
SLP	0.952	0.884	0.828	0.885
range, TX to RX (R3)	19000.000	19000.000	19000.000	19000.000
F, GHz	0.545	0.545	0.545	0.545
target RCS, Aeff, m ² (σ)	20.00	20.00	20.00	20.00
range, target to RX (R2)	3600.00	8700.00	12900.00	17300.00
ant. gain target to RX (Gr)	11.70	11.70	17.00	17.00
ant. gain, TX to RX (Grxt)	-10.00	-20.00	-20.00	-20.00
ant. gain, TX (Gtx)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
TX power, dBm, (Ptx)	90.00	90.00	90.00	90.00
range, TX to target (R1)	22600.00	27700.00	31900.00	36300.00
RX power, from TX (Pr2)	-32.75	-42.75	-42.75	-42.75
RX power, from target (Pr1)	-81.67	-91.10	-90.44	-94.12
Pr1 - Pr2	-48.91	-48.35	-47.69	-51.37
target/noise (FCM / FDW)	6.074	6.017	6.080	6.016
sampling interval	9.766E-07	9.766E-07	9.766E-07	9.766E-07

Table 1 *continued*

SYSTEM SUMMARY	case(5)	case(6)
NTT1	1024.00	1024.00
NTT2	512.00	512.00
SLP	0.858	0.938
range, TX to RX (R3)	19000.000	19000.000
F, GHz	0.545	0.545
target RCS, Aeff, m ² (σ)	40.00	40.00
range, target to RX (R2)	21300.00	9300.00
ant. gain target to RX (Gr)	17.00	17.00
ant. gain, TX to RX (Grxt)	-20.00	-9.00
ant. gain, TX (Gtx)	0.00	0.00
TX power, dBm, (Ptx)	90.00	90.00
range, TX to target (R1)	40300.00	28300.00
RX power, from TX (Pr2)	-42.75	-31.75
RX power, from target (Pr1)	-93.82	-83.55
Pr1 - Pr2	-51.07	-51.80
target/noise (FCM / FDW)	6.038	6.070
sampling interval	9.766E-07	9.766E-07

In the above tables, R_2 is adjusted so that the target/noise ratio at the output of the final Doppler analysis process is ~ 6 dB. The lowest level of received target signal is -94.12 dBm in case (4) above, and is ~ 20 dB above the KTB noise floor (-114 dBm at $+25$ C and bandwidth ≈ 1.0 MHz) at the 1.024 MSPS sampling rate.

Fig. 22 Illustrating the overall process gain for a weak signal. The test file defined parameters were: Doppler = 29 cycles, delay $Z = 23$, $K_2 = 0.005$, and $K_4 = 1.0$. For analysis, $R_1 = 512$, $N_1 = 512$

This is a limiting case for illustrating overall process gain for the **Fig 2** algorithm, and limited to a single path only (i.e. $RYA(*,*)$) to intentionally bypass the sieve filter. The target/reference amplitude ratio in the synthetic target file generator was adjusted so that the processed target signal amplitude in the analysis code was roughly twice the average noise level FDW. Although this is an imprecise criterion, it provides a lower limit on the actual processing gain G_p .

Using (15) and (16), and for $K_4 = 1.0$, $K_2 = 0.005$, $SLP = 0.995$, $FCM/FDW = 2.73$

12 Reference signal level reduction

The archetype canceller topology is shown in Fig. 23 . As used here, the term *weight* denotes a complex (in-phase and quadrature) RF multiplier. Branch outputs E_2 and E_3 include fixed time delays T_2 , T_3 and complex weight elements U_2 / θ_2 and U_3 / θ_3 that can each scale and rotate an input signal through any angle $-\pi$ to π . The addition of separate time delay elements (e.g. T_2 , T_3) to each weight path was previously found to increase the instantaneous bandwidth of the null at the cost of decreasing the peak value of the null ^{[5], [12]} .

In all models here, the fixed time delays T_n and complex weight properties are assumed to be frequency independent. The remaining weight values $U_2 \dots U_3$ are subsequently adjusted (either manually or using a control loop) to minimize the output power at E_S over the selected IF bandwidth. Over a time scale $\approx (1/F_0)$ the complex weight values can be considered fixed and frequency-independent for the purposes of vector analysis.

When $(G_{RMX} - G_{MMT}) > \sim 8$ dB, the multipliers $U_2 \dots U_3$ can be realized with conventional mixers, as in Fig. A.3.2 . In practice, a double-balanced diode mixer used in this way will exhibit an attenuation of 4 to 6 dB from the 'R' to 'LO' port when the 'I' port is biased with the maximum allowed DC current. When the 'I' port is biased at zero volts, the 'R' to 'LO' port attenuation can be ~ 30 dB or more. If $(G_{RMX} - G_{MMT})$ is significantly less than ~ 8 dB, it is not possible to bias the mixer(s) to an attenuation low enough to achieve cancellation unless attenuation is added to the target path.

Fig. 23 Vector canceller

Here, both the target and reference RF signals from the target antenna flow through the T+R channel to the output summer at A_S , and the reference signal flows through the R channel.

In Fig. 23, each of the paths E_n has a net transfer function

$$E_n = U_n e^{j(\omega t + \theta_n - T_n \omega)}$$

A *local** minimum value of the output E_S occurs when:

$$d(E_1) / d\omega + d(E_2) / d\omega + d(E_3) / d\omega = 0$$

$$\sum |d(E_n) / d\omega| = 0$$

For each E_n ,

$$d(E_n) / d\omega = d(U_n e^{j(\omega t + \theta_n - T_n \omega)}) / d\omega = U_n (t + \theta_n - T_n) \cdot e^{j(\omega t + \theta_n - T_n \omega)}$$

and since the θ_n are by definition constant and the T_n are arbitrary,

$$d(E_n) / d\omega = U_n (-T_n) \cdot e^{j(\omega t + \theta_n - T_n \omega)}$$

$$|d(E_n) / d\omega| = U_n \cdot T_n$$

Although the *requirement* for broadband cancellation is

$$\sum U_n \cdot T_n = 0 \tag{20}$$

(20) is still not sufficient since the phases θ_n must be correctly adjusted.

* i.e. one combination of $U_2, U_3, \theta_2, \theta_3$, which yields a broadband minimum of E_S for a chosen set of delays T_2, T_3 .

For $F_0 = 540 - 550$ MHz

$T_0 = 8.0$ $T_2 = 0.0$
 $\theta_0 = 0.0$ $\theta_2 = -0.879$
 $U_0 = 0.50$ $U_2 = 0.498$

broadband_corr_trial_04C100_UHF1.xls

Fig. 24 Cancellation result for a single weight

In the above case, the weight path E_3 is omitted. This is the hardware configuration used for the actual range sensor, as further detailed in the Appendix.

When T_2 is equal to T_0 , $\text{abs}(U_0 - U_2) / U_2 < .001$ and $\theta_0 = (\theta_2 - \pi)$, the suppression level is < -90 dB and constant over the entire band.

For $F_0 = 540 - 550$ MHz

$$T_0 = 8.0 \quad T_2 = 4.0 \quad T_3 = 7.63$$

$$\theta_0 = 0.0 \quad \theta_2 = -2.01 \quad \theta_3 = 0.116$$

$$U_0 = 0.50 \quad U_2 = 0.238$$

$$U_3 = -0.262$$

broadband_corr_trial_04C100_UHF3.xls

Fig. 25 Cancellation result for two independent weights, 8 nsec delay, T_2 set to 4 nsec

For $F_0 = 540 - 550$ MHz

$$T_0 = 8.0 \quad T_2 = 5.0 \quad T_3 = 7.55$$

$$\theta_0 = 0.0 \quad \theta_2 = -2.29 \quad \theta_3 = 0.124$$

$$U_0 = 0.50 \quad U_2 = -0.301$$

$$U_3 = 0.198$$

broadband_corr_trial_04C100_UHF5.xls

Fig. 26 Cancellation result for two independent weights, 8 nsec delay, T_2 set to 5 nsec

13 Physical target measurements

In this system, the gain prior to the SDR demodulators is set by the same command line that initiates the sampling process. Excessive SDR gain results in a higher percentage of samples with amplitude peaks at -127 or $+128$. Ideally, an automatic gain control (AGC) feature would utilize software that examines the SDR output and adjusts the commanded gain so that the saturation percentage is less than some specified maximum value. As this feature was beyond the scope of the project, only manual control of the gain was employed. At the beginning of every measurement session, and after a brief warmup period to allow the SDR gain to stabilize, the saturation rate of a test file was measured and the SDR gain was adjusted to limit the percentage of saturated values in a batch to 1% or less.

The ATSC transmission format includes a pilot signal located approximately 309 KHz above the lower frequency bandedge^[36] and power level specified as 11.3 dB below the average data signal power. During early trials of the autocorrelation system, SDR operation nearer to the pilot frequency (542.309.. MHz) resulted in an inconsistently higher level of non-target noise than at higher frequencies. As a result, the SDR band center frequency was moved to 546.3 MHz for all further target data collection trials.

Fig. 27 recorded description: "...jet a/c, 0.75 x standard range, east to west..", overlap window PKC = 128 , NKC = 256, range = $8.06E+3$ m , physical range $R_2 = 4.03$ km, Doppler = 257 Hz

Fig. 28 recorded description: "...jet a/c, standard range, east to west..", overlap window PKC = 128 , NKC = 256, range = 2.04E+4 m , physical range $R_2 = 10.2$ km, Doppler = 193 Hz

Fig. 29 recorded description: "...jet a/c, standard range, east to west..", overlap window PKC = 64 , NKC = 256, range = 2.04E+4 m , physical range $R_2 = 10.2$ km, Doppler = 194 Hz

Fig. 30 recorded description: "...jet a/c, 0.5 x standard range, east to west..", overlap window PKC = 128 , NKC = 128, range = 5.08E+3 m , physical range $R_2 = 2.54$ km, Doppler = 41.3 Hz

Fig. 31 recorded description: "...jet a/c, standard range, east to west..", overlap window PKC = 256 , NKC = 128, range = 7.4E+4 m , physical range $R_2 = 3.7$ km, Doppler = 134 Hz

14 SDR software command detail

It is assumed here that the source(s) of the SDR to USB interface firmware and the details of its installation and use will be continually revised. Accordingly, these details are not included here. For this work, the relevant combination was:

SDR firmware: gqrx-2.11.5.dmg
Mac OS Mojave ver. 10.14.6

For the above combination, and in the following example, the Terminal application is used to define the operation of the SDR and save the collected data to a specific file:

operating frequency, Hz	546300000
sampling rate per second	1024000
RF gain ⁵ , dB	29.5
number of samples ⁶	550000
arbitrary file name	dJ546_3_248.dat

the corresponding command is entered in Terminal:

```
rtl_sdr -f 546300000 -s 1024000 -g 29.5 -n 550000 dJ546_3_248.dat
```

which generates a response in Terminal:

```
Using device 0: Generic RTL2832U OEM  
Found Rafael Micro R820T tuner  
[R82XX] PLL not locked!  
Sampling at 1024000 S/s.  
Tuned to 546300000 Hz.  
Tuner gain set to 29.70 dB.  
Reading samples in async mode...
```

Note that, for the Nooelec NESDR, when using the software listed above, and for a wide range of specified "Tuned to" frequencies, the string "[R82XX] PLL not locked!" was always present in the terminal response as shown above. In every case, as verified by an external signal generator, the SDR operating frequency was within 0.5 PPM of the programmed frequency.

5 The RF gain number assigned in the Terminal is resolved to the nearest value in a list of (apparently) fixed and standard gain values applicable to the tuner portion of the SDR. A list of gain values is found in [38] as:

```
Supported gain values (29): 0.0 0.9 1.4 2.7 3.7 7.7 8.7 12.5 14.4 15.7  
16.6 19.7 20.7 22.9 25.4 28.0 29.7 32.8 33.8 36.4 37.2 38.6 40.2 42.1  
43.4 43.9 44.5 48.0 49.6
```

6 A single sample is a *pair* of in-phase and quadrature baseband *byte formatted* values in the output data file, so there are 1.1E+6 data values for the example shown.

15 A/D quantization options

This part describes how quantization affects the FFT/correlation/IFFT process. Note that while all of the digital processing within the analysis code is always accomplished using the default VB floating point accuracy, quantization will be applied to only the *signal waveform* values FKI(*) and FKQ(*) created by the synthetic target generation code.

First, a baseline or reference result was generated with the default target generator code previously used. Figure 34 shows the output of the analysis code when when the synthetic data file representing a very weak signal ($K_2 = 0.007$) is saved with the default 8 bit quantization. When the same FKI(*) and FKQ(*) values were quantized to 4 bits, the resulting range–Doppler plot was essentially identical to Fig. 34, and is not shown here.

The FKI(*) and FKQ(*) values were then quantized to 2 bits as shown in Fig. 33. Although the change in the range–Doppler plot (Fig. 35) was not investigated in detail, it is graphically evident that the target to noise ratio is only slightly degraded when compared with the 8 bit baseline result.

While it is unlikely that a commercial SDR product would exhibit such low accuracy, a 4 bit flash A/D would have the singular advantage of very high speed, since it could be realized with 4 high speed comparators and a small network of logic gates.

Fig. 32 2 bit quantization (4 levels)

TEST_DSMP_HG7S_418JC.txt $K_2 = 0.007$, $KF1 = 2.0$

The 8 bit synthetic target file series created for gain analyses did not incorporate amplitude limiting to the range (126,128). Accordingly, amplitude limiting was not used for the above 4-level synthetic target file.

The sequence below is a sample of the above file *_HG7S_418JC.txt:

```
.
.
5069, -159, 52
5070, -53, 52
5071, 158, -159
5072, 52, 52
5073, -53, 52
5074, 52, -53
5075, -53, -53
5076, 158, -53
5077, 52, -53
5078, -53, 52
```


Fig. 33 The standard 8 bit result for the weak signal $K_2 = 0.007$

Fig. 34 The 2 bit (4-level) result for the weak signal $K_2 = 0.007$

For the same target level, the background noise for the 2 bit case is slightly higher than in the standard 8 bit case. The *pattern* or distribution of the pixel noise is different than in the 8 bit case.

16 Conclusions

A passive range and Doppler sensor was assembled from conventional hardware, including a widely available SDR module. Other than the defined sieve filter, no other special processing was used subsequent to the minimum FFT/correlate/IFFT/FFT code required for range Doppler analysis. The commodity PC used for this work required ~10 seconds to process a single batch of data comprising $2.62E+5$ samples collected in ~0.25 second at a 1.024 MSPS SDR sample rate. The high ratio of processing time to data collection time effectively limits this specific system to usage in batch mode rather than in real time mode. With the exception of the SDR to USB interface software, all processing and display code was implemented in VB6.

Despite the location of the system in a heavily urbanized area and the low antenna height above ground level, target returns were received at range from 2.5 km to 10 km, in approximate agreement with analytical predictions.

PC configuration: ASUS CM1831, 64-bit OS, AMD FX-8120 eight-core processor, clock rate 3.1 GHz; Win 7 Pro, Visual Basic 6

Bibliography

- [1] P.E. Howland, D. Maksimiuk and G. Reitsma, "FM radio based bistatic radar", IEE Proc. Radar Sonar Navig., Vol. 152, No. 3, June 2005, doc. no. a17a3652111ad0a9.pdf
- [2] W. Feng, J.-M. Friedt, G. Cherniak and M. Sato, "Passive bistatic radar using DVB-T receivers as general-purpose software-defined radio receivers", Aug 2018, http://jmfriedt.free.fr/dvbt_hardware.pdf
- [3] H.D. Griffiths, "Passive Bistatic Radar and Waveform Diversity", Nov 2009, NATO/OTAN doc. no. ADA567763
- [4] Abdullah, et. al. "Moving target detection by using new LTE-based passive radar", Progress In Electromagnetic Research (PIER) 2015, doc. no. 10.15070901.pdf
- [5] W. D. White, "A Multiple-Beam Architecture for Sidelobe Cancellers", IEEE Transactions On Aerospace and Electronic Systems, Vol AES-23, No. 5, Sep 1987, pp. 612-619
- [6] Heng-Cheng Lin, "Interference Canceler with Difference Beam" [sic], US Patent 4697188, Sep 29, 1987
- [7] K. W. Forsythe, "Utilizing Waveform Features for Adaptive Beamforming and Direction Finding with Narrowband Signals", Lincoln Laboratory Journal, Vol. 10, No. 2, 1997
- [8] N. A. Mohamed, J. G. Dunham, "A Low-Complexity Combined Antenna Array and Interference Cancellation DS-CDMA Receiver in Multipath Fading Channels", IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communication, Vol. 20, No. 2, Feb 2002
- [9] Eli Brookner, "Adaptive Beam Forming Apparatus", US patent 4720712, Jan 19, 1988
- [10] S. P. Applebaum, et. al. , "Multiple Intermediate Frequency Side-Lobe Canceller", US patent 4044359, Aug 23, 1977
- [11] D. M Brady, et. al. , "Adaptive Interference Suppression Arrangement", US patent 4320535, Mar 16, 1982

- [12] J. Ward, R.T. Compton, Jr. , "Performance Analysis of Large Adaptive Sidelobe Canceller Arrays with Reused Elements", Ohio State University Electroscience Laboratory, final report 719711-1, doc. no. DTIC AD-A212888, June, 1989
- [13] P. W. Howells, "Intermediate Frequency Side-Lobe Canceller", US patent 3202990, Aug 24, 1965
- [14] http://www.analog.com/media/en/technical-documentation/dsp-book/dsp_book_Ch12.pdf
- [15] S. Searle, L. Davis, J. Palmer, "Signal processing considerations for passive radar with a single receiver", IEEE – ICASSP 2015
- [16] Y.W. Lee, T.P. Cheatham, J. B. Wiesner, "The application of correlation functions in the detection of small signals in noise", Technical Report No. 141, Research Laboratory of Electronics, MIT, Oct. 13, 1949
- [17] P.E. Howland, "Television Based Bistatic Radar", Thesis, University of Birmingham, Sept 1997
- [18] D. Moser, G. Tresoldi, C. Schüpbach, V. Lenders, "Design and Evaluation of a Low-Cost Passive Radar Receiver Based on IoT Hardware", IEEE 2019
- [19] Y. L. Lim, "The Modelling and Simulation of Passive Bistatic Radar", Thesis, University of Adelaide, March 2013
- [20] Peter. P. Viezbicke, "Yagi Antenna Design", U. S. Department of Commerce, NBS Technical Note 688, Dec 1976
- [21] 4NEC2 can be sourced from: <https://www.qsl.net/4nec2/>
- [22] E. Ali, A. Örstadius, "Passive Radar Detection of Aerial Targets", MS Thesis, FOI, Swedish Defense Research Agency, May 23, 2017
- [23] <https://sourceforge.net/projects/gqrx/>

[24] <http://www.nooelec.com/store/sdr/sdr-receivers/nesdr-smart-sdr.html>

[25] "List of software-defined radios" (Wikipedia) "NooElec NESDR SMARt" (<http://www.nooelec.com/store/sdr/sdr-receivers/nesdr-smart-sdr.html>).
retrieved Oct 28, 2017.

[26] aircraft speed restrictions are per "FAA Instrument Procedures Manual",
FAA-H-8083-16B_Chapter_3.pdf (2017)

[27] detail on the internal structure of the RTL2832U demodulator is available here:
<http://datasheetcafe.databank.netdna-cdn.com/wp-content/uploads/2015/09/RTL2832U.pdf>

[28] Microsoft Visual Basic 6.0 Professional (aka VB98/VB6.exe , file size 1836 kb
6/25/1998)

[29] W. H. Press, et.al., "Numerical Recipes", Cambridge University Press, 1989,
ISBN 0-521-38330-7

[30] <https://social.msdn.microsoft.com/Forums/vstudio/en-US/bb373c4f-6da3-4a63-b58c-263715ea54fe/serious-rnd-problem?forum=vbgeneral>

[31] <https://www.experts-exchange.com/articles/11114/An-Examination-of-Visual-Basic's-Random-Number-Generation.html>

[32] Aaron Scher home page:
http://aaron.scher.com/wireless_com_SDR/home.html
Dr. Aaron Scher aaron.scher@oit.edu Oregon Institute of Technology (2015)

[33] Aaron Scher RTL-SDR detail:
http://aaron.scher.com/wireless_com_SDR/rtl_sdr_info.html

[34] Aaron Scher capturing I and Q data:
http://aaron.scher.com/wireless_com_SDR/RTL_SDR_AM_spectrum_demod.html

[35] http://aaron.scher.com/wireless_com_SDR/docs/Some-Measurements-on-E4000-and-R820-Tuners.pdf

[36] Advanced Systems Television Committee, "ATSC Digital Television Standard – Part 2: Transmission System Characteristics", Doc. A/53 Part 2:2011, Dec 15 2011, a_53-Part-2-2011.pdf

[37] for Rafael R820T:
https://rtl-sdr.com/wp-content/uploads/2013/04/R820T_datasheet-Non_R-20111130_unlocked.pdf

[38] <https://web.stanford.edu/class/ee179/labs/Lab2.html>

A.1 Autocorrelation mathematical detail

The following is not a rigorous proof, but it summarizes the relationship between the input data $x(t)$ and the range IFFT output.

A common definition of the autocorrelation function is

$$A(t) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} x(t)x^*(t - \alpha) dt \approx \sum_{-m}^{+m} x(t)x^*(t - \alpha) dt$$

where

$t = [-m \cdot T_s, (-n + 1) \cdot T_s \dots m \cdot T_s]$

$T_s =$ is the sampling interval in seconds

delay $\alpha = +/- p \cdot T_s$, $p \leq +m$

$x(t)$, $x(t - \alpha)$ = baseband or demodulated samples of the target and reference signals.

A multiplication property for Fourier transform pairs is

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} x(t)y^*(t) dt =$$

$$(1/(2\pi)) \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} X(j\omega)Y^*(j\omega) d\omega$$

A.1.1

In general,

$$F(u(t - \alpha)) = U(j\omega) e^{-j\omega\alpha}$$

$$F(u^*(t - \alpha)) = U^*(j\omega) e^{-(-j\omega\alpha)}$$

$$F(u^*(t + \alpha)) = U^*(j\omega) e^{+j\omega\alpha}$$

Letting

$$q(t) = x(t)$$

$$s^*(t) = x^*(t - \alpha)$$

$$Q(j\omega) = X(j\omega)$$

$$S^*(j\omega) = X^*(j\omega) e^{+j\omega\alpha}$$

Then A.1.1 becomes

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} x(t)x^*(t - \alpha) dt = \\ & (1/(2\pi)) \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} X(j\omega) X^*(j\omega) e^{+j\omega\alpha} d\omega \\ & = (1/(2\pi)) \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |X(j\omega)|^2 e^{+j\omega\alpha} d\omega \\ & = \text{IFFT}(|X(j\omega)|^2) \end{aligned} \tag{A.1.2}$$

Thus the autocorrelation $x(t), x(t - \alpha)$ is the IFFT of the squared magnitude of the FFT result and is assigned to $UAV(r, n)$ and $UCV(r, n)$ as in Fig. 3. For a target located in the range $1 \leq \alpha \leq NTT$, the envelope of the magnitudes of $UAV(r, \alpha)$ or $UCV(r, \alpha)$ over the maximum range of r has a sinusoidal variation, as in Figs 9 and 10.

A.2 SDR sampling rate, frequency offset, and I, Q phase convention

By comparison with a high accuracy external reference frequency, and after a sufficient warmup period, the frequency errors of both the NooElec SDR and an external programmable (PLL) signal generator were each verified to be less than ± 0.1 PPM at $F_0 = 545$ MHz. The worst case frequency difference between the two devices would then be $\Delta F \leq 0.2E-6 \cdot 545.0E+6 \leq 110$ Hz.

With the SDR frequency F_{SDR} set to 545.0 MHz, the external generator frequency was then programmed to a numerical value $F_{\text{EXT}} = (545.0E+6 + 740)$ Hz. Finally, $2.0E+4$ samples of the resulting SDR (I,Q) output pairs were recorded, using a sampling rate of $1.024E+6$, as plotted in Fig. A.2.1.

Fig. A.2.1 Verification of SDR I and Q output phasing sense

There are 8 complete cycles between $(13000 - 2000)$ samples = $1.1E+4$ samples

total waveform period = $(1.1E+4 / 1.024E+6) = 1.074E-2$

waveform frequency = $1 / (1.074E-2 / 8) = 744.8$ Hz

These results are consistent with the sample rate, specified SDR center frequency, and external CW input frequency. The slightly distorted appearance at the waveform maxima is due to a low comparison frequency (and consequently high phase noise) in the external phase locked loop (PLL) source.

A.3 Reference signal suppression and cancellation network detail

Fig. A.3.1 Canceller interconnect detail

The canceller used for the sensor used only the single weight $W2$.

$XF1, XF2 = 75 \text{ ohm to } 50 \text{ ohm impedance transformer}$

$ATT1 = 75 \text{ ohm to } 50 \text{ ohm resistive matching attenuator (5.7 dB)}$

$S3 = \text{general purpose, connectorized power splitter/summer (Minicircuits ZFSC-2-5 or equivalent)}$

Vector Weight (W2) detail

Fig. A.3.2 Vector weight W2 detail

M1, M2 = general purpose, double balanced diode mixer, with IF port frequency range extending to DC (Minicircuits ADEX-10 or equivalent).

QS1 = quadrature power splitter (Anaren 1F1304 or equivalent)

PD1 = general purpose, surface mount power splitter/summer (Minicircuits ADP-2-20 or equivalent)

Weight settings

As configured in Fig. A.3.2, each mixer is used as a current controlled attenuator. Each control signal (I control or Q control) *must* be configured as a (+/-) current source, or at least be current limited. A *typical* specified maximum IF port current is +/- 20 mA.

A.4 Synthetic Target file generator, code excerpt

FROM: / p_SHQ_offset_HCB/ PRN_gen_06_04Y/

```
KAA = 33 ' number of Doppler cycles per BATCH
For NZ = 0 To 402000
  NOISEB
  MKA(NZ) = V9 ' random magnitude for EACH range bin
  AKA(NZ) = 2 * pi * Rnd(1) ' random angle for EACH range bin
Next NZ
B3 = 49
NA% = 0
For NZ = B3 To 402000
  If NA% >= 256 Then NA% = 0
  SHI(NZ) = MKA(NZ) * Cos(AKA(NZ))
  SHQ(NZ) = MKA(NZ) * Cos(AKA(NZ) + (pi / 2))
  SJI(NZ - B3) = MKA(NZ) * Cos(AKA(NZ) - (2 * pi * KAA * NZ / 262144))
  SJQ(NZ - B3) = MKA(NZ) * Cos(AKA(NZ) - (2 * pi * KAA * NZ / 262144) + (pi / 2))
  NA% = NA% + 1
Next NZ

For NZ = B3 To 401100
  FKI(NZ - B3) = Int(127 * (0.02 * SJI(NZ) + SHI(NZ)) + 0.5)
  If FKI(NZ - B3) > 128 Then FKI(NZ - B3) = 128
  If FKI(NZ - B3) < (-127) Then FKI(NZ - B3) = -127
  FKQ(NZ - B3) = Int(127 * (0.02 * SJQ(NZ) + SHQ(NZ)) + 0.5)
  If FKQ(NZ - B3) > 128 Then FKQ(NZ - B3) = 128
  If FKQ(NZ - B3) < (-127) Then FKQ(NZ - B3) = -127
Next NZ
For NZ = (B3) To (250 + B3)
  REH(NZ - B3) = 1 * FKQ(NZ - B3)
Next NZ

Private Sub NOISEB()
S1 = Rnd(1)
S2 = Rnd(1)
If S1 < 0.0001 Then S1 = 0.0001
S3 = -0.5 * Log(S1)
  If S3 < 0 Then S3 = 0
  V9 = 0.785 * Sqr(S3)
End Sub
```

FILE SAVED AS: TEST_BBBE_HCL7_02D.txt

target amplitude = 0.02

A.5 Antenna Detail

The 545 MHz antenna was optimized using the EM field simulator 4NEC2^[21]. Initial dimensions from a prototype VHF antenna described in Viezbicke^[20] were used as a starting point for manual optimization in 4NEC2. The optimization proceeded in two steps. In the first step, the element lengths and spacings were adjusted to yield the highest possible (convenient) forward gain at bandcenter. In step two, the element lengths and spacings were again adjusted to minimize the antenna input impedance Q over 540 to 550 MHz subject to the constraint that the bandcenter forward gain did not decrease by more than 2 dB from from value achieved in step one.

All configurations simulated here assume:

- nonconductive boom (1.25" O.D. PVC pipe, ASTM D 1785–15)
- no ground plane, free space condition
- the driven element (DE) was extended into the + Z plane. As a result of the Z plane offset, the elevation radiation pattern is slightly asymmetric.
- all elements are 0.25" aluminum rod

Within 4NEC2, the computed results for an array in free space are independent of the array's location relative to the arbitrary (0,0,0) origin location

Fig. A.5.1 Azimuth plot, horizontal plane, $F_o = 545$ MHz

$G_{fwd}(90 \text{ deg}) = 11.77$ dB

$G_{rev}(270) = -1.88$ dB

$Z_{input} = 44.1 + j 82$

Fig. A.5.2 Elevation plot, vertical plane, $F_o = 545$ MHz
 $G_{\text{fwd}}(90 \text{ deg}) = 11.77$ dB
 $G_{\text{rev}}(270) = -0.60$ dB
 $Z_{\text{input}} = 44.1 + j 82.3$

Fig. A.5.3 Azimuth plot, horizontal plane, $F_o = 540$ MHz
 $G_{\text{fwd}}(90 \text{ deg}) = 11.6$ dB
 $G_{\text{rev}}(270) = -7.61$ dB
 $Z_{\text{input}} = 43.8 + j 62.9$

Fig. A.5.4 Azimuth plot, horizontal plane, $F_o = 542$ MHz
 $G_{\text{fwd}}(90 \text{ deg}) = 11.68$ dB
 $G_{\text{rev}}(270) = -4.97$ dB
 $Z_{\text{input}} = 43.3 + j 70.2$

Fig. A.5.5 Azimuth plot, horizontal plane, $F_o = 548$ MHz
 $G_{\text{fwd}}(90 \text{ deg}) = 11.78$ dB
 $G_{\text{rev}}(270) = +0.44$ dB
 $Z_{\text{input}} = 47.4 + j 95.8$

Fig. A.5.6 Azimuth plot, horizontal plane, $F_o = 550$ MHz
 $G_{\text{fwd}}(90 \text{ deg}) = 11.74$ dB
 $G_{\text{rev}}(270) = +1.65$ dB
 $Z_{\text{input}} = 51.8 + j 106.0$

Although the numerical values are correct, the following images are not graphically accurate.

Fig. A.5.7 Element lengths only. The two halves of the driven element are physically 5.25 inch long and are separated by a 0.3 gap for the feed network, thus the tip to tip length of the driven element is $10.8 = (2 \cdot 5.25) + 0.3$.

Fig. A.5.8 Element locations only

Note that for the NEC polar plots, angles in the X–Y plane are referenced to the (+) X axis, but the antenna elements were arranged along the Y axis as shown below. The direction of maximum radiation is along the Y axis at $\Phi = 90$ degrees.

Similarly, angles in the Z–Y plane are referenced to the (+) Z axis. Since the driven element is offset from the X–Y plane in the (+) Z direction, the direction of maximum radiation in the Z–Y plane is slightly rotated in the (–) Z direction, i.e. $\Theta = 95$ degrees as shown in Fig. A.5.2 .

Fig. A.5.9 / Fig. A.5.10

final configuration

ELE1, 2 = 5.25" antenna driven elements
cable = RG-6, 2 braid layers + two foil layers
FB1, 2, 3 = 9 mm I. D. split ferrite sleeve, P/N 2035-0930G
d1, d2, d3 = 1.6", 3.6", 5.6"

Fig. A.5.11 Approximate element values in the feed network.

DOCUMENT END